

PIONEERING SUSTAINABLE CRM RECOVERY IN EUROPEAN MINING

Funded by
the European Union

21 PARTNERS

8 COUNTRIES

7.29M FUNDING

48 MONTHS

THE PROJECT

An aerial photograph of a large-scale mining operation, showing a complex network of conveyor belts and processing equipment. The scene is dominated by dark, earthy tones, with a prominent yellow conveyor system running diagonally across the frame. The overall atmosphere is industrial and technical.

Europe's mining industry faces a major challenge - recovering critical raw materials (CRMs) from complex, low-grade ores. OPTIMINER tackles this with sustainable, tech-driven solutions that balance environmental and financial goals.

REMINER

Advanced CRM recovery technologies, powered by an AI-driven CRM Recovery Selector.

DEMOMINER

Pilot projects in Spain, Greece, Poland, Finland and Chile

DIGIMINER

A digital platform for smart monitoring and control, featuring a Decision Support System, Virtual Miner assistant, and Digital Twins

GLOBEMINER

Global awareness and EU-Chile strategic cooperation.

ECOMINER

Tools to optimise energy, water use, waste valorisation

REAL-WORLD IMPACT

USE CASES

Pilot projects
in mines across

SPAIN

SALORO and LEONORE

GREECE

TERNA MAG

POLAND

JSW

FINLAND

TAPOJÄRVI

CHILE

MINERA HASPARREN SPA

LD

FOCUS ON CRMs

Magnesium, tungsten and rare earth elements (REEs) such as neodymium, copper, cobalt, and coking coal.

12

Mg

Magnesium

74

W

Tungsten

60

Nd

Neodymium

29

Cu

Copper

27

Co

Cobalt

6

C

Coal

THE CONSORTIU

JM

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